

A Columbus's egg: the possibility of beta-glucans -induced TRIM and adaptive immunity against COVID-19, inducing cross primary and secondary prevention for pandemic shutdown worldwide. *

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Summary

SARS-COV 2, like HIV, induces NK-, CD4+, CD8+-based immune depression proportional to COVID-19 severity and immune anergy after the seventh day from the beginning of clinical symptoms, the principal cause of fatalities in older people affected by atherosclerosis-based comorbidities. Since the 2003 SARS-COV pandemic, this clinical evidence has not oriented WHO and anti-COVID 19 scientific committees to natural innate and adaptive active immunity boosting-based primary and secondary prevention and immune therapy in anergy. It represents a guilty omission, only orienting countries to mass vaccination with experimental vaccines of limited validity with unknown but clinical and scientific evidence of short-term and probable long-term adverse effects. Beta-glucans, structural polysaccharides present in Baker's yeast, cereals, algae, or exopolysaccharides in the walls of mushrooms or fungi such as *Ganoderma lucidum* (Reishi), *Grifola frondosa* (Maitake), *Lentinula edodes* (Shitake), and *Coriolus versicolor*, in evolution responsible for the defense against massive pandemics, are powerful innate and adaptive immunity boosters.

Extensively studied in cancer prevention and therapy, beta-glucans boost innate humoral immunity, neutralize immunosuppression, and induce an active humoral adaptive immunity, representing an easy, cheap, formidable weapon against SARS-COV 2 accessible worldwide, for primary and secondary prevention, and therapy at zero costs, inducing pandemic shutdown, and cross prevention against cancer and other communicable diseases.

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The lack of primary and secondary prevention of the SARS-COV2 pandemic based on the ignorance of the previous 2002 SARS-COV lesson on the depressed antiviral immunity through NK and CD 8+ inhibition, and the induced anergy after the seventh day from the beginning of clinical syndrome is the cause of the COVID-19-induced fatalities in older people with comorbidities.¹
²This omission driven by WHO and scientific committees anti-COVID 19 worldwide finds its cause in the lack of adopting the Person-Centered Medicine paradigm overcoming the wrong linear

causality approach to research and clinics.^{3 4} The nonlinear axiom is that any infection is relative to the person's natural immunity state—the buffer factor—and there is no virus (cause)-disease (effect) linear causality. The recent theory about the relativity of SARS-COV 2 entry into cells and COVID-19 evolution⁵, which confutes the determinant role of ACE-2, produced a shift toward the necessity to boost natural immunity not only in older people at risk for comorbidities but also in all people, inducing cross prevention against cancer and other communicable diseases. The theory changes the approach from mechanistic primary and secondary prevention founded on lockdowns and artificial active immunity induction. This philosophy exposed people to vaccines of doubtful experimental validity⁶ with unknown but well foreseeable hypothetical long-term adverse effects and limited actions over time and distribution problems and costs worldwide associated with an extensive international business not motivated by nonartificial prevention. Conversely, straightforward and cheap health education-based preventive measures that boost innate humoral and adaptive immunity could have saved millions of lives. An epistemological spread of ignorance about the science-based person-centered medicine paradigm caused more than one million deaths because it induced the omission of a person and people-based nonmechanistic primary and secondary prevention and early treatments blocking the pandemic.

Baker's yeast (BY) (*Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*-SC) is a beta-1,3/1,6-d-glucan polysaccharide well known for its known immune-stimulant properties. To date, clinical and scientific evidence of their significant actions against communicable and noncommunicable diseases has not been applied in prevention and clinics and has not divulged.

Beta-glucans (BGs) are structural polysaccharides present in cereals, algae, or exopolysaccharides in the walls of mushrooms or fungi such as *Ganoderma lucidum* (Reishi), *Grifola frondosa* (Maitake), *Lentinula edodes* (Shitake), and *Coriolus versicolor*. Polysaccharides inhibit hexokinase 2, representing an essential inducer of cancer cell apoptosis because they block the source of cancer cell energy and downstream glycolysis, as in viral anti-allostasis. The *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (SC) membrane contains on average 55% beta-glucan, together with approximately 19% mannans, 15% protein, 6% fat, and 3% ash⁷. Zymosan is a protein-carbohydrate complex extract from SC cells with the glycidic fraction represented by 1- 3 β glucan. It is recognized by APCs' TLR2 (Toll-like receptors 2) and Dectin1 receptor family and raises macrophage activation and phagocytosis. The physio-pathological challenge is to ascertain whether beta-glucans could play a significant role in SARS-COV-2 prevention and therapy, as in cancer. L. Legentil, F. Paris, C. Ballet et al. in 2015 extensively highlighted beta-glucan receptors.⁸ They bind to CR3, Langerin, carbohydrate-binding modules, glycolipids, such as lactosylceramide (present also on epithelial cells), scavenger receptors, and inflammasome proteins, which promote IL1- β production downstream. Beta-glucans bind to NK cells, monocytes, macrophages, dendritic cells, B cells, and neutrophil receptors through these receptors⁹. Beta-glucans activate macrophages and promote phagocytosis, ROS production, and cytokines and chemokines. The specific beta-glucan receptor Dectin-1 enhances the TLR 2-mediated activation of ERK-MAPK, which mediates IL 10 secretion and inhibits IL12 and IL6 secretion highly produced in SARS-COV 2 dendritic cells. TNF β secretion by F4-80+ macrophages in the splenic red pulp was found by Dillon S, Agrawal S, Banerjee K. in 2006.¹⁰ The authors showed in vitro that Zymosan induces a tolerogenic response and a fragile clonal expansion and proliferation of antigen-specific T cells and minimal production of Th1 and Th2 cytokines but high levels of IL-10. The induction of IL 10 represses the induction of proinflammatory cytokines, including IL 12, IL 6, and TNF- α .

This zymosan anti-inflammatory induction could be of clinical interest for inhibiting a cytokine storm. Beta-glucans inhibit the NLRP3 inflammasome and downstream IL-1 β . In contrast to other opposite experimental and clinical observations, this anti-inflammatory effect could be explained by a hormesis effect: low doses induce immune suppression through IL 10, while high doses (higher than 200 μ g/ml-up to 500) induce inflammatory responses with IL 12 secretion. It activates the TH1 axis, resulting in a shift from the cancer M2 immunosuppressive environment and in SARS-COV

anergy in atherosclerotic people. A probable relative condition is the BG chemical structure used in experiments: soluble zymosan has different effects from nonsoluble formulations.

Epigenetic modifications mediate beta-glucan action. B. Novakovic, E-Habibi, SY Wang, et al.¹¹ in 2016 discovered that beta-glucans reverse the epigenetic state of LPS-induced immunological tolerance. BGs epigenetically reprogram LPS-induced tolerant macrophages, allowing a restoration of macrophage responsiveness. It is the key to understanding the crucial role of B glucans in sepsis patients. It could appear in contrast with the zymosan tolerogenic response but probably depends on the chemical formulation of the molecule and the hormesis effect.

This observation is significant at the preventive and clinical levels because COVID-19 severity is related to a tolerance state inducing anergy shared by older people with atherosclerosis-based comorbidity¹². Reversing tolerance in anergic patients is the first clinical objective, and it is also relevant for primary prevention, which must be addressed to induce a nontolerant immune environment to prevent anergy in older people. Tolerance opens doors to infections^{13 14} T-reg-mediated tolerance characterizes immunosenescence, the primary cause of vulnerability to infections and cancer.

A prevention strategy is to use factors breaking anergy such as IL 2 – stimulation by Baker's yeast and/or immune stimulants such as melatonin.¹⁵ An excellent preventive strategy is the straightforward measure of anergy existence in older people to promote an easy Baker's Yeast TRIM. A. Geller, J. Yan,¹⁶ starting from several publications, stated the importance of stimulating trained immunity (TRIM), which induces metabolic, mitochondrial, and epigenetic reprogramming following exposure to an initial stimulus in a memory phenotype of enhanced immune responses. This suggests using TRIM inducers such as Baker's yeast to boost immune responses, prevent COVID-19 clinical syndrome, and treat anergy. Baker's yeast stimulates the TH1 and IL 2 response,¹⁷ and breaking anergy is essential in prevention and therapy through melatonin production through a fermentation process in the gut laboratory.¹⁸

Immunostimulation with beta-glucans reduces the RNA expression of TGF beta 2, reduces mRNA expression of TGF beta 1 in lung tissue, and increases cytotoxic T-cells in thoracic lymph nodes as M.H. Monaco, B.D Pence, J.A. Wood et al. depicted in 2013¹⁹. Beta-glucans prevent immunosuppression through TGF beta 1inhibition.

In 2000 BR Lúdvíksson, D Seegers, AS Resnick, Strober W²⁰ depicted that TGF-β has differentiated immunosuppressive effects at many levels by a persistent suppression over time if naïve-t-cells are exposed to the cytokine during priming resulting in T cells with severely impaired secondary immune responses, even if TGF-β is not present during secondary stimulation

²¹Many investigations have confirmed that β glucans inhibit tumor growth in murine carcinoma models, human melanoma, neuroblastoma, mastocytosis, lymphoma xenograft models, and ovarian, breast, lung, and gastric cancer. They convert M2 protumor immunosuppressive macrophages into an M1-like antitumor phenotype by promoting NK and CD8+ T cell cytotoxicity as well as a decrease in myeloid-derived suppressor cells and regulatory T cells. BGs have been studied for their solid anticancer action,^{22 23 24} more than for their antiviral action.

The beta-glucan receptor Dectin-1 is the primary β-glucan receptor on myeloid DCs, macrophages, monocytes, and B cells and has a pivotal role in promoting antiviral and anticancer activity through IRF5-Syk-induced IFN B synthesis.²⁵ Dectin-1 in DCs triggers the production of the inflammatory cytokines TNF-α, IL-6, IL-2, and IL-23 through its cytoplasm. SARS-COV 2 infection prevention

is possible with high doses of beta-glucan-mediated conversion from a TH2/M2 immune-suppressive phenotype to a Th1 inflammatory phenotype by preventing anergy in older people at risk and promoting CD4⁺-CD8⁺ recovery, inducing a TH1/M1 phenotype. It is also essential for cancer prevention and treatment. Epidemiological investigations with new parameters and clinical trials are necessary to confirm the hypothesis well supported by scientific evidence, considering the difficulty of panvaccine production without adverse effects and the impossibility of vaccinating the entire world.

Dectin-1 receptors are very present on lung epithelial cells and APC dendritic cells (DCs), playing an essential role in natural adaptive immunity above the described domain containing an immuno-receptor tyrosine-based activation motif (ITAM), phosphorylation of downstream kinase *Syk*, and adaptor protein caspase recruitment domain 9 (CARD9). Dectin 1 binding with beta-glucans induces Th17 and Th1 responses. Th17 antagonism with Tregs can explain the antianergic role of beta-glucans. Viral and cancer cell N-glycans inhibit the NK-induced first defense. However, beta-glucan binding to dectin-1 receptors via the *Syk* pathway triggers nuclear translocation of IRF5 and induction of genes such as *Fam26f*, which are known to increase the tumoricidal activity of NK cells. S. Leibundgut-Landmann F. Osorio²⁶, GD Brown et al. in 2008 showed that²⁷ DCs exposed to dectin-1 agonist-induced antigen-specific expansion of TCR transgenic CD8(+) T cells and their differentiation into CTLs in vitro, evidencing the role of the dectin-1/*Syk* pathway in coupling innate immune recognition of beta-glucans to all branches of the adaptive immune system, including CD4(+) T helper cells, B cells, and CD8(+) cytotoxic T cells. ***The theory that zymosan alone acts by stimulating memory CD8 T-cells in the lung has been confirmed. In 2019 by I. Caminsc I, M.H. Lahoud, A. Pizzolla, L. M. Wakim discovered that zymosan alone activated CD8+ T cell memory (CD8-TCM) in lung tissue and used it as a vaccine adjuvant, boosting the influenza virus vaccination effects on CD8-TCM.*** This confirms the immune-stimulating properties of zymosan TRIM resulting in CD8 memory cell production and its ability to enhance specific CTLs. The immune action of zymosan to produce CD8⁺ MCs in the lungs confers Zymosan a vital role by preventing lung complications of SARS-COV-2 infection in anergic patients, but the problem is identifying an adequate dose of IL 10 for zymosan induction. Baker's yeast appears to be preferable in prevention and therapy as an IL 2 agonist, such as melatonin.

Clinical investigations showed that perioperative administration of beta-glucans reduced serious postoperative infections or death by 39% after high-risk noncolorectal operations. Clinical studies confirmed that beta-glucans induced clinical immune stimulation of bacterial and viral infections. They caused a significant reduction in the incidence of the pulmonary lesion score and viral replication rate in SIV-infected pigs at the experimental preventive level (swine influenza virus) and an increase in the concentrations of interferon-gamma (IFN-gamma) and IFN-mediated nitric oxide (NO) in bronchoalveolar lavage fluid from pigs preadministered beta-glucans and infected with SIV.²⁸

The N and C domains of BG agglutinins and adhesins bind to N-glycans²⁹ and consequently with COVID-19 viral glycoproteins through their N-terminal globular domains, which bind peptide or sugar ligands with millimolar and nanomolar affinities. BGs in such a way interrupt the immune escape strategy through N-glycans explained by A. C Walls, M. A Tortorici, B Frenz et al. studied the α human coronavirus NL63 (HCV-NL63).³⁰ B-glucan binding to spike proteins dampens virus adhesion to ACE-2 in lipid rafts, where Dectin-1 is activated by beta-glucans or zymosan localized similar to SARS-COV 2.^{31 32} N-glycan terminals of viral S-glycoproteins bind to the *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* membrane mannose but probably also to other complex carbohydrates and induce C3-mediated opsonization as lectin-binding proteins. ***Beta-glucans activate innate humoral immunity and inhibit virus attachment to DC-SIGN and Dectin 1 receptors and***

epithelial-endothelial cells to ACE 2. Viral N-glycans bind to the NK CD 337 receptor in such a way that they infect immune cells. However, beta-glucan binding could inhibit this process by occupying receptors, saving NK/induced antiviral action. Baker yeast and mushroom saccharides binding to viral S-glycoproteins generate an antigen complex (SGLY-BGLU) that can be read by APCs DC-SIGNr, Dectin-1, and probably other C-carbohydrate classical lectin family receptors. Receptor occupation inhibits virus entry into immune cells and enables antigens to activate MHC2 antigen presentation to T cells and prime B cells. It produces a natural vaccine effect, determining activation and proliferation and B-cell priming leading to specific immunity. The role of beta-glucans as antigen carriers³³ and humoral immunity enhancers was confirmed in 2016 by K. Baert, BG De Geest, H. De Greve³⁴. The existence of an immunogenic complex binding to specific and non-specific lectin receptors in immune cells like NK, CD8, neutrophils, macrophages is revealed by the evidence of an increased titer of antibodies against influenza virus in animals pre-treated with beta-glucans as V. Vetvicka, J. Vetvickova J. discovered in 2015, documenting the existence of TRIM.³⁵

Immune complexes determining specific adaptive immunity explain *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*'s role in human evolution, defending humanity from tremendous pandemics and contributing to their extinction. The 2002 SARS-COV pandemic ended without mass vaccinations. As underlined above, B-glucan-s-glycoprotein antigens are processed by APC MHC2 and prime B lymphocytes for specific antibody production by plasma cells. This beta-glucan immunogenic action could be the "Columbus egg" against SARS-COV-2 and other viruses, inducing natural immune protection worldwide, which is a more potent artificial vaccine because beta-glucans stimulate innate humoral immunity. B glucans determine three levels of prevention:

Inhibition of virus binding to immune cell receptors;

Direct stimulation of natural humoral immunity induces virus opsonization through complement;

Formation of immune complexes with the virus inducing downstream adaptive immunity;

Infected circulating monocytes, macrophages, neutrophils, naive T cells, and immature DCs are the early principal virus propagation inducers if the virus binding to their receptor is not inhibited. Their infection leads to the initiation of viral gene transcription, viral protein synthesis, lack of IFN- β induction through viral proteins and virus transfer by DCs to susceptible cells, and different pathways for ARDS³⁶. Along with the Dectin 1 activation of innate-adaptive humoral and cellular immunity, C3 receptors bind to the complex BG-S-glycoproteins through their iC3b fragment proteolyzed fraction activated by serum factor I. In SARS-COV-2, potent complement activity has been associated with disease gravity. These iC3b fragments promote the attachment of iC3b-opsonized pathogens to the iC3b receptors (CR3, CD11b/CD18) of phagocytic cells and NK cells, stimulating phagocytosis and/or cytotoxic degranulation.³⁷

Primary receptors on DCs and macrophages are members of the TLR and C-type lectin receptor (CLR) families, such as Dectin-1. They recognize mannan-binding proteins and beta-glucans, representing the most studied adhesion receptors of SARS-COV-2, with ACE2 present on macrophages but not on DCs.

Y. L. Lin, ss Lee, sM Hou, BL Chiang in 2006³⁸ depicted the *Ganoderma Lucidum* (Reishi mushroom)(1-->6)-beta-d-glucan effects on human DCs. They demonstrated that genes associated with phagocytosis (CD36, CD206, and CD209) decreased, and genes associated with proinflammatory chemokines (CCL20, CCL5, and CCL19), cytokines (IL-27, IL-23A, IL-12A, and IL-12B), and costimulatory molecules (CD40, CD54, CD80, and CD86) increased, documenting how BG stimulates T cell activation and B cell priming through costimulatory CD40-CD80-CD86-

CD54 necessary to APCs for T cell effector activation. IL 12 produced by the interaction of APCs CD 40 and T cell CD40L induces the TH1 effector subset, and NK cells induce IFN γ production and activate APCs and downstream CD8⁺ production, while IL 23 secretion by TH 17 cells and IL 27-induced anti-inflammatory activity inhibit it. It could appear synergic to the low doses of zymosan inducing IL 10 immunosuppressive effects previously reported, and probably it depends on the hormesis effect and the chemical structure, but zymosan is only a fraction of the yeast cells. This variability could explain the decisive immune-stimulant action of BG and clinical results against cancer and CD8⁺ T cell memory induction. Differences between Lin, Lee, Hou, and Chiang's research results and Dillon, Agrawal, and Banerjee's research results could probably depend on the biochemical difference of the whole wall structure between *Saccharomyces*, Maitake, Shitake, and the partial extract from Zymosan. Mushroom BGs have short b (1, 6)-linked branches from the (1,3) backbone. Yeast b-glucans have b (1,6) branches elaborated with b (1,3) regions. Beta-glucan immune modulation appears to be related to differences in polysaccharide chain length, branching extent, length, and molecular weight. Most likely, all baker yeast and mushroom cells have opposite effects from those of only zymosan, whose effects are, in any case, dose-dependent. The confirmed APC activation by mushroom BG and IL 12 induction confirm that these activate T cell and downstream B cell priming, resulting in antibody production. Activated T Cell CD 40L binds to CD40 B-cells, constituting the necessary signal 2 for B cell activation. CD 80 (B7-1)-CD 86 (B 7-2) are APC costimulatory signals expressed with MHC2 antigen presentation. The T helper cell line CD 54 binds to CD 11 and CD 18 of B cells, priming B cell activation. Beta-glucans stimulate APC and NK activation, maturation of naïve T cells by T effector cell activation, B cell priming by T cells, IL 12 stimulation inducing a natural-cellular immune reaction and an active humoral reaction by inducing the production of specific antibodies, and activating TRIM inhibition in immunosenescence. The SGLY-BGLU immune complexes assume immunogenic properties, such as a natural conjugate vaccine, crucial in COVID-19 prevention in an infection incubation time, SWAB-positive asymptomatic people or at the beginning of the disease. In advanced infections and anergy, as occurs in older immunosenescent people, comorbidities, or immune-depressed patients, Baker'Yeast and mushrooms could be used to induce TRIM by promoting blunted innate immunity.

Baker Yeast's beta-glucans binding to DC, Monocytes/Macrophages, C-type lectin receptors DC-SIGN (C-type lectin DC-SIGN (DC-specific ICAM-3-grabbing non-integrin), 1-Dectins, 3C, Langerin, and Lactosyl-ceramide receptors highly expressed also on plasma membranes of human epithelial cells and neutrophils, makes Baker's Yeast and the mentioned mushrooms' BGs potent molecules for training innate and the adaptive immunity. Boosting the natural-adaptive immune system should be the first target of TRIM-based intelligent primary prevention for older people at severe COVID-19 risk.

The "Curfew policy and "Green Pass" policy result from the Donkey syndrome pandemic, induced by a WHO unable to conceive an adequate prevention strategy since 2002. Baker's Yeast is sold in supermarkets and is available worldwide. Health education to boost immunity and an antiviral diet can block SARS-COV-2 and other viral pandemics, inducing cross-prevention against cancer. Blocking SARS-COV-2 adhesion to DCs, macrophages, NK cells, and neutrophils, boosting innate humoral immunity means defending the downstream cascade of cellular natural and adaptive antiviral immunity thanks to NKs, PCs, TH1 helper cells, and CD8 cytotoxic T cells and promoting adaptive immunity through early antibody production.

In synthesis, beta-glucan use in SARS-COV-2 and other virus infection prevention and treatment is based on the following synergic effects.

1. *B-glucan-induced effective immune training (TRIM) through innate immunity stimulation; BG binding to specific receptors, such as dectin-1 family, CR3, lactosyl-ceramide, selected*

- scavenger receptors, TLR-2/6,³⁹, and DC-SIGN/R inhibition of virus binding to receptors; and BG competition for binding (barrier effect).*
2. *Induction of innate humoral immunity through C3-mediated virus-infected cell opsonization (probably partial 50%), such as cancer cells⁴⁰;] activation of neutrophil and macrophage phagocytosis.*
 3. *Probable induction of the opsonization-mediated S-glycoprotein conformation change inhibiting virus adhesion to ACE2 receptors (to be confirmed)*
 4. *Adaptive specific immunity stimulation through the immunogenic action of the S-protein-BG complex and specific APC antigen presentation activating T cells.*

Suppose Baker's yeast's BG or mushrooms are assumed at the early stage of SARS-COV-2 infection, a TRIM effect and the induction of adaptation induced by the SGLY-BGLU complex could represent a good, rapid, cheap, and readily available prevention program compared to unuseful vaccination programs for older immunosenescent people, also exposing them to adverse effects. In SWAP-positive, asymptomatic patients, at the beginning of any, not diagnosed infection, beta-glucan TRIM and adaptive immunity-induced actions are real "Columbus eggs" to induce a natural vaccination and to block the infection in an early, not dangerous phase, with the use of other natural and cheap, potent virucide substances available to all people, with a self-care approach.

The constitution of a beta-glucan TRIM-induced metabolic-immune shield against SARS-COV-2 extends its preventive action to other viruses and cancer prevention. C3 (complement) action implementing lung inflammation does not suggest using C3 activators in an advanced and severe clinical syndrome⁴¹ where an IFN gamma-induced NO and other cytokine storms are signaled by high hyperpyrexia (strong IL 1-IL 6-TNF α induction). Conversely, in an easily diagnosed energy before the infection and signaled by patients with a low fever and interstitial pneumonia and lymphopenia after the 7th day since the beginning of the clinical syndrome, characterized by an immune-suppressive phenotype, such as in older patients with comorbidities, TH1-IL 2-mediated immune stimulation appears necessary. Beta-glucan administration alone and or with other TH1 stimulators, such as melatonin, could be precious and save lives.

The use of beta-glucans in primary and secondary prevention is part of the "person and people prevention approach (PPPA)"⁴². People's immunity boost, the result of the person-centered medicine nonlinear and deterministic paradigm, was wholly omitted by WHO and the world anti-SARS-COV committees, as in Italy. It appears a financial draw to make countries slave of few health and life merchants. Since 2002, health merchants have not produced any vaccine against SARS. COV, like HIV, probably for awareness of the viruses' mutations high frequency, and in 2003 the SARS-COV pandemic and 2010 MERS disappeared without mass vaccinations. The mechanistic and guilty omission of non-mechanistic primary and secondary prevention, cutting off fundamental human rights, results from the more severe Donkey syndrome pandemic (DSP) than SARS-COV 2. People with DSP have not yet learned the science-based paradigm shift of medicine, and the health concept to date has been assessed as "The choice of the best possibilities for being the best human person," linking health to freedom, responsibility, and dignity, derived by person-centered medicine.⁴³

In contrast, health education based on a healthy life quality induction comprising antiviral nutrition and accessible natural preventive measures, the basis of PPPA, is the most significant way to stop any pandemic, with the benefit of inducing cross-prevention of other communicable and non-communicable diseases such as cancer.

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